

SURFACE WIND AND WAVE HEIGHT PREDICTION FOR THE QEII STORM
USING SEASAT SCATTEROMETER DATA

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Abstract

The sea state associated with the developing Queen Elizabeth Storm II (1200 UT 9 Sep 78 to 0000 UT 11 Sep 78) is hindcast with a fine resolution spectral wave model. The surface winds are provided by a limited area, fine resolution (100 km) numerical weather prediction model. Forecasts from initial conditions which included and excluded SEASAT scatterometer surface winds were performed. Surface wave height hindcasts were made utilizing surface winds provided by the atmospheric models. When the SEASAT winds are allowed to influence the upper levels, a larger positive impact is found.

1. Introduction

In recent years the requirements for accurate forecasts of sea state have increased substantially. Over the vast oceans, efficient routing of shipping to save fuel as well as avoiding the loss of men and materials from high seas demand accurate wave forecasts. The development of offshore mineral reserves requires detailed wave height climatologies along continental margins.

Wave forecasts depend upon the accuracy of the winds provided by a numerical weather forecast, the method that converts those model winds into surface winds and the wave prediction model itself. Wave prediction models have recently become quite sophisticated. In addition to propagating the waves at their group velocity, some incorporate the reflection of waves due to bathymetric variations (see Golding, 1983). Waves are generated as the wind blows on the water surface, energy is transferred between different wavelengths through nonlinear interactions, and wave energy is dissipated by wave breaking or bottom drag.

The development of numerical weather prediction (NWP) models has been the subject of intense efforts since the early 1950's. Improvements to NWP models have occurred through improved numerical techniques, increased resolution and more realistic physics. Although numerical models have undergone continuous improvements, the coverage and availability of different sources of data have lagged behind. For example, over the oceans conventional data is limited to surface temperature and pressure reports from ships and buoys as

well as a few upper-air reports from weather ships and island. In June 1978, however, a new source of wind data over the world's oceans became available with the launch of the SEASAT-A satellite. Although the satellite survived only three months, it provided a wealth of data which could be used in data impact studies.

In this paper we present results of NWP and wave height forecasts when the initial condition either includes or excludes SEASAT data. We shall concentrate on an explosive case of oceanic cyclogenesis in the North Atlantic where the nascent cyclone was observed by SEASAT. In this particular case, the conventional data sources and the corresponding operational NWP forecasts were very poor. These poor forecasts had dire consequences. The ocean-liner Queen Elizabeth II encountered the storm's 30 m/sec winds and 39 ft. seas, resulting in about \$50,000 in damages and injuring about 20 passengers. The fishing trawler Capt. Cosmo reported 15 to 20 foot waves off Georges Bank late on 8 September 1978 and disappeared on the 9th.

In Sections 2 and 3 we give a brief description of the NWP model and wave forecast models. In Section 4 we show how we modified the NMC analysis when we included SEASAT-A wind data. Section 5 gives the forecast results from the NWP and wave height model from initial states which included and excluded SEASAT data. Our conclusions are presented in Section 6.

2. Numerical weather prediction model

The NWP model is essentially that described by Duffy (1981). The coordinate system used in the model is a Lambert conformal map projection which is true along 30°N and 60°N. The vertical extent of the model ranges from 100 mb to 1000 mb and has a vertical resolution of 100 mb. All the dependent variables are located at all of the grid points (i.e. the A-grid). The horizontal resolution of the model is 100 km. The overall domain is 4900 km by 4900 km, centered on 60°W.

The horizontal components of the wind and geopotential heights are located at the 100, 200, ..., 1000 mb surfaces while the mixing ratio, thickness and omega are at the intermediate levels. The atmosphere is assumed dry above 300 mb. Spatial derivatives are second-order except where steep topography blocks the flow through the control volume

and then one-sided differences are used. The equations are essentially written in flux form.

An important aspect of the model is the use of split-explicit time-differencing scheme of Gadd (1978) to integrate the finite-differenced equations of motion, continuity, thermodynamics and water balance. This scheme integrates the governing equation by separating all those terms associated with linear, inertial-gravity wave motion from the slower, meteorological wave. Those terms representing inertial-gravity waves are integrated with a forward-backward technique suggested by Masuda (1981). For a one-dimensional, linearized shallow water model, Masuda showed that the low frequency, meteorological wave is preserved almost perfectly while the high frequency gravity waves were damped effectively. The highest frequencies are damped most strongly.

The remaining advection terms are integrated with a modified Matsuno scheme suggested by Kurihara and Tripoli (1976). By the appropriate blending of the predictive and corrective stages of the Matsuno scheme, they showed that the damping associated with the Matsuno scheme can be completely eliminated. The overall scheme is very efficient because the computationally expensive advection terms need to be integrated only one third as often as the inertial-gravity terms.

The physical parameterizations included in the model are large-scale and convective precipitation, evaporation of rain or snow as it falls through the atmosphere and sensible and latent heat fluxes from the surface. A dry convective adjustment scheme is also present. A detailed description is given in Duffy (1981).

3. Wave prediction model

The wave prediction model is based on the model described by Golding (1983). The continuous spectral wave energy is approximated by ten frequency bands from 0.07 Hz to 0.25 Hz, in intervals of 0.02 Hz. The waves can propagate in twelve directions. The depth of water at any given grid point was interpolated from a Scripps' bathymetric data set with a resolution of 1° by 1°.

Golding used a modified Lax-Wendroff integration scheme. We have chosen to use a new scheme suggested by Takacs (1984). The scheme is similar to Lax-Wendroff scheme but has the characteristics of a three-step third-order scheme. In the one-dimensional case with $\mu = c_g \Delta t / \Delta x$, the predictive stage for i th grid point is given by

$$q_i^* = q_i^{(n)} - 1/2 [F_{i+1/2} - F_{i-1/2}] \quad (1)$$

$$\text{where } F_{i+1/2} = \mu_{i+1/2} (q_{i+1}^{(n)} + q_i^{(n)}) - |\mu|_{i+1/2} (q_{i+1}^{(n)} - q_i^{(n)}), \quad (2)$$

c_g the group velocity, Δx the distance between grid-points i and $i+1$ and Δt the time step. The corrector step gives the actual value of q at the new time and is given by

$$q_i^{(n+1)} = q_i^{(n)} - 1/4 [P_{i+1/2} - P_{i-1/2}] + \frac{\alpha}{2} [(Q_{i+1/2} - Q_{i-1/2}) - (R_{i+1/2} - R_{i-1/2})] \quad (3)$$

where

$$P_{i+1/2} = (\mu + |\mu|)_{i+1/2} (q_{i+1}^* + q_i^{(n)}) + (\mu - |\mu|)_{i+1/2} (q_i^* + q_{i+1}^{(n)}) \quad (4)$$

$$Q_{i+1/2} = (\mu + |\mu|)_{i+1/2} (q_{i+1}^* - q_i^{(n)}) + (\mu - |\mu|)_{i+1/2} (q_i^* - q_{i+1}^{(n)}) \quad (5)$$

$$R_{i+1/2} = [(\mu + |\mu|)_{i+1/2} (\mu + |\mu|)_{i-1/2}]^{1/2} (q_i^* - q_{i-1}^{(n)}) - [(\mu - |\mu|)_{i+1/2} (\mu - |\mu|)_{i+3/2}]^{1/2} (q_{i+1}^* - q_{i+2}^{(n)}) \quad (6)$$

The parameter α is empirically chosen so that the total error is a minimum and is typically equal to 0.25. To illustrate the scheme's ability to handle the advection of localized disturbances with steep gradients, the scheme was used to solve the advection equation $q_t + uq_x = 0$ in a solid-body rotational flow. A cone-shaped disturbance having a base diameter of 10 grid - points is the initial condition (see Figure 1). The exact solution would merely propagate the cone around the center of rotation without any change in shape. In Fig. 1 we have presented the numerical solution where μ varies between 0 and 0.3 and $\alpha = 0.2$ at (a) quarter, (b) half, (c) three quarter and (d) one full revolution. The scheme has approximated the exact solution very well.

At grid points adjacent to the coast, we cannot use this scheme because it uses values from two grid points away from the center. Consequently at those points we used simple upstream differencing. This scheme is a very dissipative and insured that no waves would be reflected from the shore.

The refraction scheme is based upon a continuous form of Snell's law. As Golding (1983) showed, the refraction portion of the wave energy equation is given by

$$(\Delta E)_\theta = - \Delta t \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \{ (c_g \cdot \nabla \theta) E \} \quad (7)$$

where

$$c_g \cdot \nabla \theta = - \frac{|c_g|}{k} \left\{ \sin \theta \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} - \cos \theta \frac{\partial H}{\partial y} \right\} \left(\frac{-k^2 \operatorname{sech}^2(kH)}{\tanh(kH) + kH \operatorname{sech}^2(kH)} \right) \quad (8)$$

where k is the wavenumber, θ direction of propagation, and H depth of water. Centered differences are used to compute the H derivatives. Eq. (7) is solved by using upstream differences in flux form. See Golding (1983) for details.

INITIAL CONDITION

Fig. 1. Numerical integration of $q_t + U q_x = 0$ in a solid body rotation about the center using the numerical scheme described in the text.

The growth of waves driven by surface winds is modelled in two ways. The direct forcing by turbulent fluctuations at the surface generates high frequency waves if the difference between the direction of wave propagation and wind is less than 90°. An exponential term resulting from the interaction of existing waves with a sheared low-level air flow is allowed to affect waves of all frequencies provided

$$U \cos(\theta - \psi)/c > 1 \quad (9)$$

where U is the wind speed, c the phase speed and ψ the direction of the wind. The exact formulation is given by Golding and our value of his β_1 is 0.225×10^{-3} .

The nonlinear interaction calculation devised by Golding are the most unique aspect of his model. Essentially, he defines a wind-sea spectrum which consists of all the wave energy (1) above the frequency of $0.8 f_p$ where f_p is the peak frequency and (2) where the difference between the direction of propagation and the wind direction is less than 90°. This wind-sea spectrum is forced to conform to JONSWAP spectrum (Hasselmann et al., 1973) because it is assumed that nonlinear interactions will always act to bring the wind-sea spectrum back to the JONSWAP spectrum.

Wave energy is dissipated by wave breaking and bottom friction in shallow water. The dissipation by wave breaking is given by

$$5 \times 10^{-4} f^2 E(\underline{x}, f, \theta) \left\{ \int \int E(\underline{x}, f, \theta) d\theta df \right\} 0.25. \quad (10)$$

The bottom drag is computed from an equation given by Collins (1972).

Although the model has dissipative mechanisms, sometimes these dissipation functions did not exactly balance the input when the fully developed spectrum was reached. Consequently the total energy at a particular grid point was never allowed to become larger than the average for the Pierson-Moskowitz spectrum:

$$\bar{E}_{pm} = (1.4g/U)^{-4} \quad (11)$$

The wave height model was started from a state of rest. The surface winds were provided by the winds at either the 900 mb or 1000 mb surface. If the sea-level pressure was 1000 mb or above, winds from the 1000 mb surface were used. If the sea-level pressure was below 1000 mb, then an empirical relationship by Findlater et al. (1966) was used which relates 900 mb values to those at 19.5 m. The surface winds were updated every simulation hour.

4. Initial conditions

Numerical weather forecasts were made from initial conditions which included and excluded SEASAT-A data. For the experiment without SEASAT data, hereafter called the control, we used the global analysis from the National Meteorological Center for 12 UT 9 September 1979. The terrain fields was provided from a U. S. Air Force data tape at

the resolution of 1° by 1°. Sea surface temperatures were obtained from a global dataset from the Fleet Numerical Oceanographic Center. All these fields were interpolated to the model's grid by simple bilinear interpolation. In Fig. 2 we present the initial sea-level pressure analysis. For both the control and SEASAT experiments the mass field was identical.

Fig. 2. The initial sea-level pressure analysis for 12 UT 9 September 1978.

For the SEASAT experiments, the 1000 mb winds were replaced by subjectively dealiased SEASAT winds wherever they were available. See Baker et al. (1984) for details on how the SEASAT data was prepared. In Fig. 3 and 4 we show the differences between the analysis containing SEASAT data and the control. These figures show that the differences are substantial and the swaths of satellite data are clearly discernable. The differences over the land are created because we passed a simple smoother over the SEASAT wind field to eliminate inconsistency between the data from within the satellite swath with that exterior to the swath. Consequently some wind values over land were changed by this procedure.

During the early studies, we only modified the 1000 mb winds. Experiments run from these initial conditions showed that the SEASAT winds had little impact on the numerical forecast. Over oceanic regions, the first guess field dominates the analysis because of the lack of data. Consequently, although the analysis may be incorrect, it is consistent in both the vertical and horizontal directions because a numerical model provides the first guess. When we only modified the 1000 mb winds, we created inconsistencies between the winds at 1000 mb and the upper levels. Therefore, as the model began to run, the model tried to reestablish some sort of balance. The effects of the unmodified mass field and upper-level wind fields simply overwhelmed our modifications. Because of these results we modified the upper-level winds as well as the 1000 mb winds. Our first attempt was to take the differences between the SEASAT and control 1000 mb wind analyses and add these differences to the upper-level winds. We reduced these barotropic corrections with height because the correlation be-

Fig. 3. Differences between the 1000 mb zonal wind analysis given by SEASAT minus the control.

Fig. 4. Same as Fig. 3 except for meridional winds. Between the winds at the surface and the upper levels decreases with height (Yu and McPherson, 1984). In Fig. 5 and 6 we have shown the impact of these changes on a cross section of the analysis near 40°N.

5. Results

The results from the two different numerical forecasts are presented in Figs. 7 and 8. In both cases the low located just off Nova Scotia has moved out into the open waters of the North Atlantic Ocean. In the case of the control, the low has intensified slightly, the central pressure at 36 hrs being 1000 mb and peak winds of 21 m/sec. Our results are slightly better than those given by the operational limited-area, fine-mesh model run at the National Meteorological Center (NMC) and the Navy's operational model. Numerical simulations of the QEII by Anthes *et al.* (1983) showed no intensification when only conventional data was included.

From Fig. 8 we see that the inclusion of SEASAT data has had a dramatic effect on the cyclogenesis. The lowest pressure at 36 h is now 988 mb and the peak winds are 37 m/sec. A preliminary study of the results indicates that the deepening of the low occurs because of larger amounts of convective precipitation in the SEASAT experiment than the control.

Fig. 5 Cross-sectional differences between the zonal winds of the SEASAT analysis minus the control near 40°N.

Fig. 6. Same as Fig. 5 but for meridional winds.

Experiments with a weaker vertical correlation were tried. The effect of halving the vertical correlation results in a low with a central pressure of 992 mb. The position of the low was unchanged.

The effects of adding SEASAT data in a wave height forecast are shown in Figs. 9 and 10. Winds from the control were used in the wave height forecast shown in Fig. 9 whereas winds from the

Fig. 7. The 36 h predicted sea-level pressure field for the control experiment.

Fig. 8. The 36 h predicted sea-level pressure field for the SEASAT experiment.

Fig. 9. The 36 h significant wave height forecast (in m) for the control experiment.

Fig. 10. Same as Fig. 9 except for SEASAT experiment.

SEASAT experiment were employed in the results shown in Fig. 10. In both figures we see two regions of maximum significant wave heights, each one associated with a cyclone. In the case of the SEASAT experiment, the wave heights associated with the QEII storm are 9 m higher than in the control off the coast of Nova Scotia.

6. Conclusion

Our results show that SEASAT-A data can be important in defining the initial conditions that result in rapid maritime cyclogenesis. The improved forecasts yield in turn substantially improved significant wave height forecasts. Currently work is under way to determine the best way to couple the surface winds to the upper levels in global atmospheric models.

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